

STRATEGIC PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN FOR IN-SERVICE TEACHER CERTIFICATE PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 5

Pages: 486-500

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2977

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14772665

Manuscript Accepted: 11-15-2024

Strategic Professional Development Plan for In-Service Teacher Certificate Program

Amie P. Matalam*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This descriptive study seeks to examine the proficiency level of teachers in the context of Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and to come up with a professional development plan for proper career pathing. The respondents of this study were the in-service teacher certificate holders of secondary schools coming from the Davao City division. Data were gathered through survey questionnaire containing the seven domains of PPST. Results show that secondary school teachers are highly proficient across the different domains of the PPST. When grouped by career stages, Teachers I to III rated themselves highly proficient. Additionally Master Teachers I and II are on the distinguished level for learning environment domain, and highly proficient for the rest. The ten least rated indicators were the bases for the proposed professional development plan anchored on the highly proficient qualities and standards of the PPST. It was recommended that the proposed professional development plan must be incorporated in educational institutions' professional growth program for teachers.

Keywords: *program, professional development, strategic, certificate*

Introduction

An increasing urgency exists for states and school districts to get a skilled teacher into every classroom. The Philippine policy on No Child Left Behind Act of 2001 stipulates that by the end of the School Year 2005-2006 school year, all public school teachers must be "highly qualified." That means all teachers must meet a set of standards that include demonstrated competency in each subject they teach.

Beginning teachers enter classrooms today with high expectations for themselves and for their students. Yet, the first year of teaching is a sobering experience for most new teachers, and that, over the course of one year, teachers experience a decreased strength of belief in their own efficacy and in the learning potential of their students (Harris and Associates, Inc., 1991). Nearly every study of retention in the teaching profession identifies the first three years as the riskiest on the job, the years in which teachers are most likely to leave. The dropout rate is highest among teachers in hard-to-staff, urban schools, which have the most difficulty both attracting and then retaining fully certified teachers (Ingersoll, 2001; Urban Teacher Collaborative, 2000).

According to OECD (2005), several Western countries show a recurring shortage of teachers. Recruiting and retaining teachers prove to be very challenging and problematic in many countries. Countries, such as England, for example, 40 percent of those who start teacher education never become teachers (Kyriacou & Kunc, 2007). Moreover, 40 percent of the 60 percent who completed teacher education in England left the profession within the first five years (Kyriacou & Kunc, 2007). Australian research estimates that 30 percent leave the profession during the same period (Watt & Richardson, 2007). Ingersoll (2003) also reports that only 48 percent of American teachers who graduated in 1993 were teaching five years after graduation.

In the Philippines, the findings of Gonong (2014) revealed that teachers in the Philippines performance on content knowledge was poor. The study revealed that teachers from both the elementary and high school are poor in English and Math subjects. The need for professional training and learning was on top imperatives for teachers. They emphasized their importance of enhancing their practice.

The study of Tolentino (2015) exposed the pedagogical incongruence among public school administration in Davao City. Teachers are critical to the academic success of children; the profession needs to attract and retain the best and brightest. The most serious consequences arise from the pervasive irregularities that permeate the job placement transactions of the public schools, DepEd's Schools Division, District offices, and the surest way to fix it is to make sure that Filipinos are given the best possible education by qualified teachers.

For this reason, the process of choosing and appointing teachers to teaching positions is outlined in the Teachers Hiring Guidelines. City and provincial educational offices are expected to comply with the relevant provisions of these laws and related policies when appointing teachers to teaching positions. Yet, not all schools division and district heads comply with the laws and policies when appointing teachers to teaching positions (Tolentino, 2015). Some of them comply with only some provisions while systematically flouting others in their appointment of others. Anecdotal evidence and teacher appointment data indicate that there are serious problems underlying teacher job placement issues and practices at the educational system.

The foregoing identified problems prompted the researcher to profile teachers who undergo alternative certification according to career stages utilizing the concept of PPST. The researcher sees that teachers should follow a career path as they go along the teacher job. Thus, the conduct of this research may provide vital issues and concerns to the teachers, school administration, and DEPED officials through strengthening its professional development program. Hence, the result of this study will give relevance and is appropriate to teacher certificate holders.

The results of this study will also be beneficial to the teacher certificate holders since it would bridge the gap between career stage and teaching competency. Further, this study will guide teachers to follow a career path for self-improvement.

It is with these scenarios that the researcher is motivated to pursue this study. This academic work seeks to determine issues and challenges that may hinder teachers' attainment of quality instruction. Moreover, this study identifies whether teacher certificate holders are meeting the professional standards of teaching and 21st education.

Research Questions

The intention of this study is to determine the proficiency of High School teachers in the context of Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) as the basis for a Professional Development Plan. The research specifically aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the proficiency profile of the High School teachers in terms of the domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers?
2. What competency gaps are existing among the high school teachers as indicated by the PPST domains?
3. What professional development plan should be developed to address the gaps on the proficiency profile of in-service teacher certificate high school teachers against the PPST domains?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive method of research in order to describe the profile of high school teachers on the seven domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. According to Calderon (2008) as cited by Alberto et al. (2011), a descriptive method of research describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. This research method is used for frequencies, averages, and other statistical calculations. Survey investigation is the best approach to descriptive method.

Survey research's ultimate goal is to know about a population, generally large, by surveying a sample of the said population. Hence, normative or descriptive survey. A series of questions are being posted to the respondents of this method. After which, the gathered data will be summarized and analyzed. Moreover, percentages, frequency distribution and other statistical tools are utilized to scrutinize survey data.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the in-service teacher certificate high school teachers from the selected Department of Education schools in Davao City. They have non-education bachelor's degree but were able to earn appropriate units to teach in the secondary level. There were five national high schools involved in the study all from the cluster 1 of Davao City Division.

Selection of respondents was done using purposive sampling. As stated by Crossman (2017), purposive sampling is a non-probability sample, where respondents are selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. This type of sampling is generally used to reach targeted samples quickly.

Table 1. Career Stage Profile of In-Service Teacher Certificate Respondents

Career Stage	Frequency	Percentage
Beginning Teachers	65	46.10
Proficient Teachers	45	31.91
Highly Proficient Teachers	31	21.99
Distinguished Teachers	0	0.00
Total	141	100.00

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of respondents in terms of their career stages. There were 141 respondents of the study. Sixty-five (46.10) of them are Beginning teachers (0 – 3 years of service). On the other hand, 31.91% or 45 of the respondents are Proficient teachers who are in service for at least 4 years. For Highly Proficient teachers who are already Masters Teachers I & II, there were 31 respondents (21.99%). However, none of the respondents were Distinguished teachers who are Master Teachers III and IV. It can be noted that during the conduct of the survey, among the chosen schools, none among the teachers were in the said category because some of them are still new in the teaching field. Some may have been teaching for a long time but never pursued higher studies nor conducted researches or speakership in order to move up on their career path.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire based on the seven domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers was utilized in gathering of data for this academic endeavor. The first portion of the instrument is about the career stage of the respondent. While the second part focuses on the different domains of the PPST, through their corresponding indicators. The PPST which is formerly National Competency-Based Teacher Standard (NCBTS) was established as teachers framework of teacher quality (D.O.N0. 42,2017). This is the quality assurance instrument assessing the competence of teachers in line with the national education standards. Through this instrument, the teacher will be able to cultivate his/her ability to identify students' learning styles, intelligences, strengths and

weaknesses (P21 framework for 21st Century Learning, 2015). Apart from the seven domains of the the PPST, teacher are guided on their career pathing. The career pathways of teachers are categorized into four which are the beginning, proficient, highly proficient, and distinguished teachers. It is stipulated in D.O 47 series of 2017 that as teachers tenure increase, his/ her career path should become higher. Beginning teachers should have taught for 0-3 years, Proficient teachers should be four years and above in teaching while Highly proficient teachers should already be Master teachers 1& 2 and Distinguished teachers should already be Master Teachers III & IV. Research instrument on PPST is found on Appendix E of this paper.

The research tool examines the first domain Content Knowledge and Pedagogy consisting of seven indicators, the second domain Learning Environment with six indicators, and domain Community Linkages and Professional Engagement has four indicators. On the other hand, the rest of the domains, namely - Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, , and Personal Growth and Professional Development have five indicators each.

Procedure

An endorsement letter from the Dean of the College of Education of the University of Southeastern Philippines (Appendix A) was acquired first to secure permission from the Davao City Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) to begin and to conduct the formal data gathering process. An approval letter was given by the SDS was obtained informing the respondent schools through their respective school heads authorizing the conduct of the study.

The approval letter coming from the Schools Division Superintendent was presented to the principals to seek permission to conduct the survey. With the consent from the principals, the survey questionnaires were given to the principal,s secretary to be administered to the respondents.

After the questionnaires were answered, the researcher retrieved them. Gathered data were then collated and tabulated that was subjected to statistical analysis with the guidance of a statistician. Lastly, the results were analyzed and interpreted based on the objective of the study.

Data Analysis

To answer the research questions, descriptive statistical were being employed to the gathered data. The following statistical tools were used to describe the proficiency level of the Cluster 1 high school teachers of Davao City Division.

The score of all respondents for each indicator and domain was analyzed using the mean. Also known as the average, the mean is one of the measures of central tendency that presents the middle most value of a data set in terms of value or central value (Math is Fun, 2018) . It is found by adding all the scores for a variable, divided by how many numbers there are.

The proficiency level of high school teachers for each indicator was determined by computing the mean of the responses for each indicator. On the other hand, high school teachers' proficiency level in each domain was identified by finding the average of all indicators under each domain. Overall proficiency level of teachers was determined by getting the mean of the domain. Moreover, the means were interpreted using the range of means presented in table 2.

Table 2. *Range of Means and Proficiency Level of Teachers*

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.00 – 1.74	Beginning Teacher
1.75 – 2.49	Proficient Teacher
2.50 – 3.24	Highly Proficient Teacher
3.25 – 4.00	Distinguished Teacher

Together with the means, the standard deviations of the data sets, in terms of each indicator, each domain, and overall PPST proficiency, were determined. This measure of variability describes how close or the spread of the scores are from mean within a data set (Lund Research Ltd, 2018). When the standard deviation is relatively small or close to zero indicates that the data scores are clustered near the mean, while a high standard deviation denotes that the data scores are more scattered from the mean (National Library of Medicine, n.d.).

Results and Discussion

Introduced in this chapter are the findings and results of the study, which were based on the lens of the respondents concerning on the career stages of in service teachers in the context of Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Details of the data were analyzed and interpreted to provide profound understanding to the beneficiaries and readers of the study.

Proficiency Profile of High School Teachers

Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The level of proficiency on content knowledge and pedagogy among high school teachers is presented in table 3. This domain of the PPST focuses on the intertwined notions of content knowledge mastery, and application of appropriate pedagogies.

Table 3. Teachers Proficiency Level on Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. apply content knowledge within and across curriculum	3.12	0.86	HP	3.00	0.88	HP	3.13	0.72	HP
2. use research – based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning	2.89	0.77	HP	2.93	0.78	HP	3.03	0.71	HP
3. use ICT positively	3.05	0.78	HP	2.91	0.73	HP	3.07	0.68	HP
4. promote strategies for literacy and numeracy	3.22	0.82	HP	3.11	0.83	HP	3.23	0.81	HP
5. utilize strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher- order thinking skills	3.06	0.83	HP	2.98	0.75	HP	3.07	0.68	HP
6. employ mother tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning	3.13	0.93	HP	2.93	0.88	HP	3.03	0.84	HP
7. apply classroom communication strategies	3.08	0.87	HP	3.18	0.87	HP	3.13	0.81	HP
Average	3.08	0.72	HP	3.00	0.67	HP	3.10	0.59	HP

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient

Among the seven indicators of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy domain of the PPST, the indicator promotes strategies for literacy and numeracy has the highest mean of 3.22 (SD = 0.82) for 0 - 3 years in-service teachers, and a mean of 3.23 (SD = 0.81) for MT I and MTII teacher. However, this indicator ranked second highest ($x = 3.11$, SD = 0.83) for teachers belonging to 4 & above years in service. All of which describes highly proficient. This shows that the teachers find ease in observing or making sure that literacy and numeracy strategies are well incorporated in their teaching-learning.

For the novice teachers (0 – 3 years in service), their next two highest rated indicators are employ mother tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning ($x = 3.13$, SD = 0.93, highly proficient), and apply content knowledge within and across curriculum ($x = 3.12$, SD = 0.86, highly proficient). As for teachers that were already in their 4th and higher year in-service, their highest rated indicator is apply classroom communication strategies ($x = 3.18$, SD = 0.87, highly proficient), and their third highest rated indicator is apply content knowledge within and across curriculum strategies ($x = 3.00$, SD = 0.88, highly proficient). On the other hand, the second and third highest rated indicators of the MT I and MT II teachers are apply content knowledge within and across curriculum strategies ($x = 3.13$, SD = 0.72, highly proficient) and apply classroom communication strategies ($x = 3.13$, SD = 0.81, highly proficient).

In terms of use ICT positively the respondents still consider themselves to be on a highly proficient level. But the results also imply that some teachers are not adept to technology as implied by being one of the least rated indicators by the respondents (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.05$, SD = 0.78, highly proficient; 4 & above years: $x = 2.91$, SD = 0.73, highly proficient; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.07$, SD = 0.68, highly proficient). Preservice teachers in the 21st century are technology savvy. The students in the 21st century have grown up in a fast-paced digital world, and easily tune out of the traditional lecture- based classroom. Researching, communicating and even online job applications across the world via computer or cell phone is a snap for them. Social networking sites (SNS) are only as good as the content their users share (Burke et al., 2009). To effectively engage and teach generation Z students, preservice teachers will help the educational system meet this requirement. The school systems must be outfitted with a prerequisite of ICT resources, and curricula must be designed to promote a collaborative learner-centered environment to which students will relate and respond. As ICT is integrated into classrooms, teachers must have professional development in utilizing social media in instruction.

While the teachers still consider themselves to be highly proficient in the use of research – based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning, it has one of the least means (0 – 3 years: $x = 2.89$, SD = 0.77; 4 & above years: $x = 2.93$, SD = 0.78; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.03$, SD = 0.71) among the content knowledge and pedagogy indicators. This is in consonance in the study of Maslo & Kiegelman (2008) which stated that one of the important challenges for universities and academic institutions today is their continuation as the backbone of society, providing the knowledge and educating young people for addressing complex global challenges. Within the international framework, according to the Bologna process the orientation of master studies in Europe tends to reach substantial improvement of a new generation of learners and offers opportunities for originality in idea development and use, including research. Purposefulness of the research in different rapidly changing and turbulent contexts reinforces the needs of all stakeholders – children, families, professionals and the policy audiences (Maslo & Kiegelman, 2008). It is evident that pedagogical research is complex in nature and none of the existing methodological approaches can be sufficient to discover its complexity.

Overall, for content knowledge and pedagogy domain of the PPST, the preservice teachers perceive themselves as highly proficient (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.08$, SD = 0.72; 4 & above years: $x = 3.00$, SD = 0.67; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.10$, SD = 0.59). This indicates that the respondents see that they are practicing a high level of performance on the indicators of this domain consistently.

Learning Environment. Table 4 shows the level of proficiency on the learning environment domain of high school teachers. On this domain, respondents evaluate how proficient they are in providing and securing a setting favorable for learning. In this domain of the PPST, the respondents see themselves to be at the distinguished in a number of indicators.

Under the indicator promote a fair learning environment, the respondents rated themselves as distinguished teachers (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.29$, SD = 0.90; 4 & above years: $x = 3.29$, SD = 0.82; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.32$, SD = 0.75). A mean of 3.28 (SD = 0.89) and 3.36 (SD = 0.71) for 0 – 3 years and MT I and MT II teachers, respectively, show distinguished perception on themselves for the indicator

support for learning participation. On the other hand, a distinguished level of proficiency is perceived by 4 & above years ($x = 3.32$, $SD = 0.80$, and MT I and MT II ($x = 3.37$, $SD = 0.72$) teachers for the manage classroom structure and activities indicator. For these, the respondents associate their teaching to be on the highest standards and being at par with the best practices on a global level.

Table 4. *Teachers Proficiency Level on Learning Environment*

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. adhere to learner safety and security	3.23	0.93	HP	3.22	0.85	HP	3.42	0.72	Di
2. promote a fair learning environment	3.29	0.90	Di	3.29	0.82	Di	3.32	0.75	Di
3. manage classroom structure and activities	3.20	0.86	HP	3.32	0.80	Di	3.37	0.72	Di
4. support for learning participation	3.28	0.89	Di	3.24	0.86	HP	3.36	0.71	Di
5. promote purposive learning	3.17	0.91	HP	3.23	0.86	HP	3.36	0.71	Di
6. manage learner behavior	3.11	0.91	HP	3.16	0.82	HP	3.29	0.69	Di
Average	3.21	0.84	HP	3.24	0.79	HP	3.35	0.65	Di

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient Di = Distinguished

Cano (2001), pronounced that promoting a fair learning environment has a large factor in teacher effectiveness which is being able to establish positive relationships with students. A teacher, who cannot communicate with his or her students, will not be effective. Research studies have shown the effects of teacher interactions with learners and found that "the degree and frequency of praise, use of classroom time, and the amount of attention given to groups or individuals have significant positive correlations to a learner's ability to learn".

One important indicator in the learning environment is managing classroom structure and activities and support for learning participation. Behavior Management and classroom management are the two variables that have the greatest impact on student learning (Marzano and Marzano, 2003). Teachers should develop classroom rules in order to communicate expectations. Stewart et al. argue: "Behavior management and classroom control are central to stimulating learning. Research has shown that teachers who are effective in managing classroom behavior are also effective in improving achievement" (p. 55). Teachers should establish a limit of three to five rules for their classrooms. These rules should be clearly stated in the beginning of the school year, posted, and reviewed frequently (Stewart et al., 1997).

To adhere to learner safety and security, the result explains that teachers should take note of the underpinning of Moos, which emphasizes the relevance of the physical setting, as part of the environmental system, to student outcomes. Moos states that 'architecture and physical design can influence psychological states and social behavior' (Moos 1979: 6). Over the years, Moos' model has influenced research on architecture and education that has identified other influences that the physical environment can have on student achievement and behavior.

The indicators promote purposive learning, and manage learner behavior show a progress of level across the stages as indicated by the means. On these gauges, the high school teachers are on highly proficient level, indicating their refined comprehension of the teaching and learning process.

Promote purposeful learning as an indicator of the learning environment dictates that teachers should use multiple interventions that accommodate the needs of the students. They should also "design and implement a number of incentive plans or rewards for appropriate behavior, and offer individual, frequent, specific, and corrective feedback about performance" (Stewart et al., 1997 p. 55). Teacher Effectiveness For over thirty years, the behaviors of teachers have been studied to determine the relationship to learner achievement" (Cano, 2001). Marzano and Marzano (2003) have found that "research has shown us that teachers' actions in their classrooms have twice the impact on student achievement.

It is noticeable that in this domain, MT I and MT II teachers rated themselves distinguished for all indicators. Additionally, the average means across the stages is increasing (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.21$, $SD = 0.84$; 4 & above years: $x = 3.24$, $SD = 0.79$; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.35$, $SD = 0.65$).

Diversity of Learners. The third domain of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers is focused on the diversity of learners. In this domain, teachers' understanding of the innate varied characteristics and experiences of learners and how they influence the teaching and learning experiences. Presented on table 5 is the diversity of learner proficiency level of the respondents.

Indicators aware of the learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.25$, $SD = 0.87$, distinguished; 4 & above years: $x = 3.18$, $SD = 0.81$, highly proficient; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.29$, $SD = 0.69$, distinguished), and conscious of learners with disabilities, giftedness and talents domain (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.20$, $SD = 0.92$, highly proficient; 4 & above years: $x = 3.18$, $SD = 0.86$, highly proficient; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.26$, $SD = 0.77$, distinguished) were scored by the respondents as the highest for this domain.

The remaining indicators also mean ratings presenting a highly proficient level among the in-service teachers. In descending order of mean, the indicators are concern with learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences, acquainted with learners in difficult circumstances, and sensitive to learners from indigenous groups.

Table 5. Teachers Proficiency Level on Diversity of Learners

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. concern with learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences	3.19	0.88	HP	3.16	0.82	HP	3.19	0.70	HP
2. aware with the learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences	3.25	0.87	Di	3.18	0.81	HP	3.29	0.69	Di
3. conscious of learners with disabilities, giftedness and talents	3.20	0.92	HP	3.18	0.86	HP	3.26	0.77	Di
4. acquainted with learners in difficult circumstances	3.07	0.93	HP	3.18	0.86	HP	3.23	0.77	HP
5. sensitive to learners from indigenous groups	3.08	0.87	HP	3.16	0.80	HP	3.16	0.78	HP
Average	3.16	0.83	HP	3.17	0.77	HP	3.23	0.67	HP

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient Di = Distinguished

Banks et al. (2005) explained that Knowledge of Diverse Learners (KDL) is increasingly recognized as an essential component of knowledge base for effective teaching as in today's schools, teachers must be prepared to teach a diverse population of students. The domain Diversity of learners resulted in an average mean scores of 3.16 (SD = 0.83) for 0 – 3 years, 3.17 (SD = 0.77) for 4 & above years, and 3.23 (SD = 0.67) for MT I and MT II, all signify highly proficient. This dictates that teachers are conscious of learners' diversity in the classroom, utilizes such information for the most appropriate instructional design, and mentor other teachers and evaluate with them strategies that are fitted to the context of the learners.

Curriculum and Planning. A teacher's national and local curricular know-how, and understanding of the interaction of the curriculum necessities are the emphasis of the fourth domain of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. The curriculum and planning level of proficiency of high school teachers is presented in table 6.

Table 6. Teachers Proficiency Level on Curriculum and Planning

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. plan and manage teaching and learning process	3.00	0.87	HP	3.04	0.80	HP	3.10	0.75	HP
2. align learning outcomes with learning competencies	3.00	0.83	HP	3.04	0.77	HP	3.10	0.75	HP
3. promote relevant and responsive learning programs	2.94	0.97	HP	3.04	0.85	HP	3.13	0.67	HP
4. collaborate with other professionals to enrich teaching practice	3.02	0.91	HP	3.13	0.84	HP	3.16	0.78	HP
5. teach and learn resources including ICT	3.06	0.81	HP	3.09	0.73	HP	3.16	0.58	HP
Average	3.00	0.79	HP	3.07	0.73	HP	3.13	0.62	HP

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient

For this PPST domain, the indicator teach and learn resource including ICT is one of the two highest rated indicator across the career stages (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.06$, $SD = 0.92$, rank 1; 4 & above years: $x = 3.09$, $SD = 0.73$, rank 2; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.16$, $SD = 0.58$, rank 1.5). The result shows that on this indicator, the respondents are on a highly proficient level that signifies that they consistently familiarize themselves with the available teaching and learning resources.

The other highest rated indicator by the respondent is collaborates with other professionals to enrich teaching practice with means 3.02 (SD = 0.91, rank 2) for 0 – 3 years, 3.13 (SD = 0.84, rank 1) for 4 & above years, and 3.16 (SD = 0.78, rank 1.5) for MT I and MT II. These are also telling of a highly proficient level of the teachers. Thus, for this indicator, teachers regularly support, mentor, and collaborate with each other and to other professions to enhance their curriculum and planning competence.

Both indicators plan and manage teaching and learning process, and align learning outcomes with learning competencies show equal means for each career stages (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.00$; 4 & above years: $x = 3.04$; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.10$). This indicates that the respondents are performing on similar level on these indicators, which are all signifying highly proficient level. Hence, teachers see themselves practicing consistently on the said indicators.

A mean of 2.94 (SD = 0.97) is the least rating for this domain by the 0 – 3 years in-service teachers, which is the promote relevant and responsive learning programs indicator. This is in contrast with the results from the other career stages. Among the 4 & above years in-service teachers, they rated themselves equally ($x = 3.04$, $SD = 0.85$) with the two previously discussed indicators. But, the said indicator is on the third rank ($x = 3.13$, $SD = 0.67$) for the MT I and MT II respondents. As the career stage progresses, the mean increases implying better performance in the said indicator. The respondents have described themselves to be on the highly proficient level for this indicator. This relates that there is an important point to make efficient in involving teachers in curriculum development, that is teachers have to be empowered in the process of curriculum development (Carl, 2009). Additionally, teachers should improve and increase in many areas, such as experience and autonomy.

In general, the results show an increasing rating by the respondents for the overall performance of each career stage in this indicators (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.00$, $SD = 0.79$; 4 & above years: $x = 3.04$, $SD = 0.73$; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.13$, $SD = 0.62$) and are all projects

highly proficient performance in this domain. The result is in conformity with the study of Carl (2009) which explains that without doubt, the most important person in the curriculum implementation process is the teacher. With their knowledge, experiences and competencies, teachers are central to any curriculum development effort. Better teachers support better learning because they are most knowledgeable about the practice of teaching and are responsible for introducing the curriculum in the classroom. If another party has already developed the curriculum, the teachers have to make an effort to know and understand it. So, teachers should be involved in curriculum development. For example, a teacher's opinions and ideas should be incorporated into the curriculum for development.

Teachers' involvement in the curriculum development process is essential in meeting the needs of society. The process of curriculum development requires teachers to act and reflect on society's needs in each stage of the development process. Nevertheless, sometimes this process which teachers are requested to follow is unclear. For example, in South Africa most teachers are not qualified and lack the necessary skills to participate in curriculum development. Their approach of participation in the process is not well defined and very difficult on teachers, so they face many challenges regarding their involvement in curriculum development (Ramparsad, 2000).

Assessment and Reporting. Table 7 shows the proficiency level of the teacher on the domain of assessment and reporting. The highlight of this domain is on the practices observed by teaching to collect, monitor, evaluate and report students' academic development and needs.

Results show that the indicator monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement has the highest mean rating of 3.29 (SD = 0.74) implying distinguished proficiency for MT I and MT II respondents. As for the other career stages, the said indicator signify highly proficient performance from the other career stages (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.19$, SD = 0.92; 4 & above years: $x = 3.18$, SD = 0.83). However, the lower career stages rated themselves higher than the MT I and MT II respondents for the indicators providing feedback to improve learning, and communicating learner needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders. But, all of which indicate that the respondents are on the highly proficient level. Teachers see the importance of these indicators to the teaching and learning process. Hence, they consistently observe practices associated with these indicators.

Table 7. *Teachers Proficiency Level on Assessment and Reporting*

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. design, select, organize and utilize assessment strategies	3.05	0.91	HP	3.11	0.89	HP	3.23	0.92	HP
2. monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement	3.19	0.92	HP	3.18	0.83	HP	3.29	0.74	Di
3. provide feedback to improve learning	3.19	0.81	HP	3.20	0.79	HP	3.13	0.67	HP
4. communicate learner needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders	3.15	0.92	HP	3.16	0.85	HP	3.13	0.76	HP
5. use assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices and programs	2.95	0.84	HP	3.07	0.86	HP	3.03	0.61	HP
Average	3.11	0.80	HP	3.14	0.78	HP	3.16	0.60	HP

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient Di = Distinguished

On the other hand, the indicator use assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices and programs has the lowest mean ratings for each career stage. As for the design, select, organize and utilize assessment strategies indicator, MT I and MT II respondents rated themselves higher ($x = 3.23$, SD = 0.92) than other career stages (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.05$, SD = 0.91; 4 & above years: $x = 3.11$, SD = 0.89). These indicators still place the respondents on the highly proficient level.

Assessment is a powerful, multipurpose tool. It enables teachers to track student progress with an eye towards informed planning, teaching and reporting. According to the result, teachers' overall level on assessment and reporting is (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.11$, SD = 0.80; 4 & above years: $x = 3.14$, SD = 0.78; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.16$, SD = 0.60) highly proficient. This means that teachers have sophisticated and exhaustive understanding of the practices associated with this domain. The results also present an increasing rating, with a minimal difference, on the overall perceived performance of in-service teachers for this domain.

In addition to these, teacher seek to ensure reliability, accountability, transparency and consistency across contexts, and to positively contribute to public confidence in the education system (Klenowski, 2012; Klenowski & Wyatt-Smith, 2012). In the state of Victoria, the curriculum with its levelled achievement standards, is to be used by teachers to inform the reports they provide to parents and students each year, detailing their progress against common achievement standards “including an indication of student progress against the age-related expected level of achievement” (Victorian Curriculum and Assessment Authority, 2014, p. 6).

Community Linkages and Professional Engagement. The level of proficiency of teachers on community linkages and professional engagement is shown in table 8. This sixth domain of the PPST centers on the teachers' responsibility to establish educational partnerships and linkages between the school and the community.

The indicator with the highest mean rating is follows school policies and procedures for 0 – 3 years ($x = 3.17$, SD = 0.91), 4 & above years ($x = 3.18$, SD = 0.81). But such indicator is only the second highest mean for MT and MT II respondents ($x = 3.19$, SD = 0.75). Conversely, the indicator promoting professional ethics with a mean of 3.23 (SD = 0.76) is highest for the MT I and MT II teachers,

but only ranks second for the rest of the career stages. Both show that the teachers are on the highly proficient level for these indicators. The results imply that among the indicators of this domain, the respondents exercise or observe them more.

Table 8. Teachers Proficiency Level on Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. establish learning environments that are responsive to community context	2.92	0.85	HP	3.04	0.90	HP	3.07	0.73	HP
2. engage parents and the wider school community in the educative process	2.70	0.92	HP	3.04	0.88	HP	3.10	0.83	HP
3. promote professional ethics	3.11	0.92	HP	3.13	0.84	HP	3.23	0.76	HP
4. follow school policies and procedures	3.17	0.91	HP	3.18	0.81	HP	3.19	0.75	HP
Average	3.04	0.84	HP	3.10	0.80	HP	3.15	0.72	HP

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient

This result can be attributed to the study of Titus (1943) who mentioned the integrative role that an ethics course was once thought to play in a college education. Seen as a way of setting students’ moral compasses before sending them off into the world of work, family and citizenship, colleges typically required students to take a course on moral philosophy and ethics in their final year and, to underscore its importance and lend an air of gravitas, the course was traditionally taught by the college president himself (Titus, 1943). The importance of ethics curriculum in higher education experienced a period of decline through the early and middle decades of the twentieth century until it re-emerged in the 1960s in the form of practical and professional ethics education (Davis, 1999). Medicine was on the cutting edge of the movement to make ethics a program-specific requirement of graduation and professional certification.

As the least rated means for all career stages, indicators engage parents and the wider school community in the educational process, and establish learning environments that are responsive to community context rally behind the other two indicators of the present PPST domain. Teachers still regard themselves to be on the highly proficient level for both indicators.

Overall, the level of community linkages and professional engagement of teachers is highly proficient. This is being reflected by the average mean ratings (0 – 3 years: $x = 3.04$, $SD = 0.84$; 4 & above years: $x = 3.10$, $SD = 0.80$; MT I and MT II: $x = 3.15$, $SD = 0.72$) as evaluated by the teachers. It is also noticeable that the mean rating increases as the career stages progresses.

The result is in support of the study of Ozor and Nsukka (2008) which stated that teachers in the community are the best means of promoting community and local development which proceeds national development. Schools should be community directed and passionate to promote the welfare of the community through extension and outreach services. Schools with leaders who are committed to effecting local development through projects and programs of extension can partner with industry, non-government organization and national agencies for resource generation to implement their specific plans for community with encouragement for further motivation to pursue extension and outreach work.

Personal Growth and Professional Development. Results on the level of proficiency of teachers for personal growth and professional development is shown in table 9. This domain’s emphasis is on the teachers’ personal and professional practices to grow in the profession.

Table 9. Teachers Proficiency Level on Personal Growth and Professional Development

Indicators	0 – 3 years			4 & above years			MT I and MT II		
	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D	Mean	SD	D
1. have established my own teaching philosophy	2.99	0.99	HP	3.05	0.89	HP	3.07	0.68	HP
2. embrace dignity of teaching as a profession	3.19	0.95	HP	3.16	0.85	HP	3.23	0.85	HP
3. maintain professional links with colleagues	3.11	0.90	HP	3.20	0.79	HP	3.23	0.81	HP
4. foster professional reflection and learning to improve practice	3.06	0.86	HP	3.20	0.82	HP	3.26	0.68	Di
5. advance professional development goals	3.14	0.86	HP	3.27	0.78	Di	3.23	0.62	HP
Average	3.10	0.82	HP	3.18	0.76	HP	3.20	0.65	HP

D = Description HP = Highly Proficient Di = Distinguished

The indicator with highest mean for the personal growth and professional development domain is advance professional development goal ($x = 3.27$, $SD = 0.78$) for 4 & above years respondents, signifying distinguished level of proficiency. However, the other career stages only see themselves to highly proficient on the said indicator with means of 3.14 (0 – 3 years) and 3.23 (MT I and MT II). These then imply that the teachers are persistently looking for their professional knowledge growth through planning for advance professional development goals.

Indicator foster professional reflection and learning to improve practice is rated the highest by MT I and MT II respondents ($x = 3.26$, $SD = 0.68$) denoting distinguished level of proficiency. The same indicator is perceived only as on the highly proficient level for the other career stages.

As for the rest of the indicators, the respondents see themselves as highly proficient. This suggest that the respondents do also

continually focus on developing their professional growth through the said indicators.

As a whole, the personal growth and professional development domain of the PPST has a mean scores of 3.10 (0 – 3 years: SD = 0.82), 3.18 (4 & above years: SD = 0.76), and 3.20 (MT I and MT II: SD = 0.65) by each career stage. These all signify a highly proficient level among the respondents. Several researches revealed that trainings and seminars help improve work performance. The pronouncement of Castaneda (2002) which states that professional development of teaching is for improving their teaching practice is revealed in the study. Educational change requires the introduction of new ideas, artifacts, procedures or processes. Innovation demands both initiative and originality. Its aim is to develop and promote change aimed at improving curricula, teaching and learning and the institutional framework in which the change occurs (Smith, 2003).

PPST Competency Gaps of Teachers

PPST Domains and Career Stages. Table 10 presents the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers profile per domain against the respondents' career stages. Overall rating per domain and per career stage are also shown.

Table 10. *Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers Profile and Career Stages of Teachers*

PPST Domains	Career Stages							
	0-3 years		4 years and above		MT I/II		Overall	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.076	0.719	3.003	0.673	3.097	0.593	3.057	0.675
2. Learning Environment	3.212	0.838	3.240	0.787	3.350*	0.649	3.251*	0.780
3. Diversity of Learners	3.163	0.829	3.169	0.767	3.231	0.670	3.180	0.772
4. Curriculum and Planning	3.003	0.791	3.071	0.726	3.129	0.623	3.053	0.733
5. Assessment and Reporting	3.105	0.800	3.142	0.779	3.161	0.599	3.129	0.749
6. Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.042	0.844	3.100	0.797	3.145	0.718	3.083	0.798
7. Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.095	0.823	3.176	0.756	3.200	0.649	3.144	0.763
Average	3.100	0.769	3.129	0.712	3.188	0.587	3.128	0.711

* = Distinguished

Categorized by career stages of the respondents, the results show that the teachers perceive themselves to be on a highly proficient level on most domains of the PPST. Only the mean rating of the learning environment domain of the MT I/II and the overall mean of the respondents on the same domain are on the distinguished teacher level. This implies that, regardless of the career stages, the respondents profess that they consistently practice high performance in most of the phases of the teaching profession. While the Master teachers I and II are already practicing global standards on the learning environment domain.

It is also noticeable that the mean rating in each domain is increasing as the career ladder rises, except for the first domain Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. It is stressed in the study of Conway et al. (2009) that defining and assessing teachers' professional knowledge and competence is not simple, neutral or universal, fixed or certain, but historically and culturally bound, subject to change and contestation. Therefore, competence statements, so as to recognize the multifaceted nature of teaching, and acknowledge the role of values, need to be clear and not over-elaborate.

In this analysis, it is observable that the teachers who have not reached the Master Teacher I and II career stages already perceived themselves to be highly proficient. Thus, in terms of the PPST domains and standards, the high school teachers indicate that they are manifesting teaching practices on or above the high level expectation.

This result concludes that teachers with master's degrees are on average more effective at raising test scores than other teachers. Teachers contribute to student outcomes in other ways as well. By documenting that master's degrees appear to lead to lower student absences, this study provides some initial—but at best limited—evidence that middle school teachers with master's degrees may be more effective than other teachers on average in developing other skills that may be important for future life success (Jackson 2012).

Further, Harris and Sass (2011) include 11 studies of the effects of master's degrees in their broader review of the effects of a variety of forms of teacher training on student achievement. The vast majority of the estimated effects of master's degrees on student achievement are zero, with only a few statistically significant positive estimates and a few negative estimates. Moreover, the new estimates by Harris and Sass based on Florida data for all three levels of schooling provide no evidence of positive effects of master's degrees. Other studies not included in the Harris and Sass review include Budding and Zamarro's 2009 study of elementary schools in San Diego, and Chingos and Peterson (2011)' study of 4th through 8th graders in Florida. Consistent with the Harris and Sass conclusions, these other studies also find either negative or no effects of master's degrees.

Least Rated PPST Domain Indicators. The indicators with the least mean ratings from the different domains of the PPST, as marked by the respondents by career stages, are shown in table 17. These least scored indicators will be the basis for the professional development plan.

Shown in table 11 are the least indicators among the career stages. It can be gleaned that the indicator, use research – based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning resulted low. This tells us that most teachers are not conscious in using research- based

knowledge and principles in teaching and learning. Likewise, the indicator, employ mother tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning is low for career stages 4 years and above and MT I and MT II. As to the indicator, use assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices and programs it has a low result for both career stage 1 (0 – 3 years) and 2 (4 & above years). Moreover, the .use ICT positively indicator also resulted low in career stages 2 and 3. utilize strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher- order thinking skills is also common between career stage 2 and 3.

Table 11. *Least Rated PPST Domain Indicators Among Teachers*

Domains	Indicators	0 – 3 years (Career Stage 1)		4 & above years (Career Stage 2)		MT I and MT II (Career Stage 3)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	1. apply content knowledge within and across curriculum			3.00	0.88		
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	2. use research – based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning	2.89	0.77	2.93	0.78	3.03	0.71
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3. use ICT positively			2.91	0.73	3.07	0.68
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	5. utilize strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher order thinking skills			2.98	0.75	3.07	0.68
1. Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	6. employ mother tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning			2.93	0.88	3.03	0.84
4. Curriculum and Planning	3. promote relevant and responsive learning programs	2.94	0.97				
5. Assessment and Reporting	5. use assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices and programs	2.95	0.84			3.03	0.61
6. Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	1. establish learning environments that are responsive to community context	2.92	0.85				
6. Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	2. engage parents and the wider school community in the educative process	2.70	0.92				

In Career stage 1, apart from the common least indicators previously mentioned, depicts the least results on indicators: engage parents and the wider school community in the educative process; establish learning environments that are responsive to community context; promote relevant and responsive learning programs. Career stage 2 also resulted least indicators in the following: utilize strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher- order thinking skills and . apply content knowledge within and across curriculum.

Lastly, Career stage 3 got the least results on indicators which are found in Career stage 1 and 2 which are use research – based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning; employ mother tongue, Filipino and English in teaching and learning; use assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices and programs; use ICT positively; utilize strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher- order thinking skills.

Conclusions

Based on the results, hereunder were the conclusions drawn by the researcher:

The profile of high school teachers based on the PPST is highly proficient.

Research gap was identified through the lowest mean score of the following indicators of the seven domains of PPST: use research–based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning (Content Knowledge and Pedagogy); manage learner behavior (Learning Behavior); .sensitive to learners from indigenous groups (Diversity of Learners); promote relevant and responsive learning programs (Curriculum and Planning); use assessment data to enhance teaching and learning practices and programs (Assessment and Reporting); establish learning environments that are responsive to community context (Community Linkages and Professional Engagement); established one’s own teaching philosophy (Personal Growth and Professional Development). On the other hand, the profile of teachers in terms of career stage is highly proficient. Also, it is identified that the Content Knowledge and Pedagogy and Curriculum and planning of teacher certificate teachers in the secondary level need to be addressed.

Based on the identified gaps, the researcher came up with a plan for professional development that will help bridge the gap.

The researcher would like to recommend the following based from the results:

The DepEd key officials and educational institutions must utilize the proposed framework for professional development as part of their faculty development program.

Educational leaders should provide more opportunities for the In-service teacher certificate holders to improve in the seven domains of PPST namely: content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learning, curriculum and planning, community

linkages and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development by encouraging to take advanced education, and to provide trainings.

Further studies should be conducted on the qualities of the teacher certificate holders to further enrich this academic work. A Qualitative research is also recommended to substantiate the result of the study.

References

- Alan M. Saks, (2006) "Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 21 Issue: 7, pp.600-619,
- Ambag, S. (2015). Assessment of competency level of pre-service teachers based on national competency-based teacher standards (NCBTS) in public school in the national capital region (NCR).*European Academic Research*, Vol. II, Issue 11/ February 2015.
- Avalos B. de los Rios, D. (2010). "Teacher identity construction in reform driven contexts: Istanbul Turkey (2010).
- Banks, J. A. (in press). Researching race, culture, and difference: Epistemological challenges and possibilities. In J. L. Green, G. Camilli, & P. B. Elmore with A. Skukauskaite & E. Grace (Eds.), *Handbook of complementary methods in education research*.
- Banks, J., Cochran-Smith, M., Moll, L., Richert, A., Zeichner, K., LePage, P., Darling-Hammond, L., & Duffy, H. with McDonald, M. (2005). Teaching diverse learners. In L. Darling-Hammond & J. Bransford (Eds.), *Preparing teachers for a changing world: What teachers should learn and be able to do* (pp. 232-274). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Bimrose, J., Barnes, S-A & Brown, J (2005) 'A Systematic Literature Review of Resarch into Career-Related Interventions for Higher Education',Manchester: HECSU
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1981) *The Ecology of Human Development. Natural and Planned Experiments*
- Brownell, M. T., Yeagar, E., Rennels, M. S., & Riley, T. (1997). Teachers working together: What learning educators and researchers should know. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 20, 340–359.
- Burry-Stock, J. A. (Ed.). (1995). *BER 450 Handbook*. Tuscaloosa, AL: The University of Alabama.
- Calderon, J.F. and E.C. Gonzales. 1993. *Methods of Research and Thesis Writing*. Manila: Great Books Trading
- Carl, A. (2009). *Teacher empowerment through curriculum development theory into practice*. Juta&Company Ltd.
- Christian, M. S., Garza, A. S., & Slaughter, J. E. (2011). Work engagement: A quantitative review and test of its relations with task and contextual performance. *Personnel Psychology*, 64(1), 89-136.
- Cochran, K. (1997). Pedagogical content knowledge: Teachers' integration of subject matter, pedagogy, students, and learning environments. *Research Matters to the Science Teacher* No. 9702, 1997.
- Coladarci, T., & Breton, W. A. (1991, April). Teacher efficacy, supervision, and the special education resource-room teacher. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, Chicago.
- Crossman, A. (2017). Understanding purposive sampling: an overview of the method and its implications. <https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3026727>
- CSC Memorandum Circular No. 3 s. 2001. Revised policies on merit promotion plan.
- Darling-Hammond & K. Bransford (Eds.), *Preparing teachers for a changing world: What teachers should learn and be able to do* (pp. 390-440). San Francisco: Jossey Bass.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2000a). How teacher education matters. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 51, 166-173.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2000b). Solving the dilemmas of teacher supply, demand, and standards: How we can ensure a competent, caring, and qualified teacher for every child. New York: National Commission on Teaching and America's Future.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2006). Assessing teacher education. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 57, 120-138.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2010). *The flat world and education: How America's commitment to equity will determine our future*. New York: Teacher College, Columbia University.
- Darling-Hammond, L. and Bransford, J. (eds) (2005) *Preparing Teachers for a Changing World: What Teachers Should Learn and Be Able to Do*. Washington: US National Academy of Education.
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Adamson, F. (2010). Beyond basic skills: The role of performance assessment in achieving 21st century standards of learning. Stanford Center for Opportunity Policy in Education (SCOPE), Stanford University, School of Education.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Berry, B., &Thoreson,A. (2006). Does teacher certification matter? Evaluating the evidence. *Educational*

Evaluation and Policy Analysis, 23, 57-77.

Darling-Hammond, L., Chung, R., & Frelow, F. (2002). Variation in teacher preparation: How well do different pathways prepare teachers to teach. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 53, 286-302.

Darling-Hammond, L., Hammerness, K., Grossman, P., Rust, F., & Shulman, L. (2005). The design of teacher education programs. In L.

David Roth and Watson Scott Swail.(2000).certification and teacher preparation in the united states. Pacific Resources for Education and learning.

Davis, K. S. (2003). "Change is hard": What science teachers are telling us about reform and teacher learning of innovative practices. *Science Education*, 87(1), 3–30.

DepEd Order No. 27 s. 2016. Qualification standards (QS) for senior high school (SHS) teaching positions in the department of education.

DepEd Order No. 3, s. 2016. Hiring guidelines for senior high school teaching positions effective school year 2016-2017.

DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017. National adoption and implementation of the Philippine professional standards for teachers.

DepEd Order No. 66, s.2007 Revised Guidelines on the Appointment and Promotion of Other Teaching, Related Teaching and NonTeaching Positions

DepEd Order No. 7, s. 2015. Hiring guidelines for teacher 1positions effective school year (SY) 2015-2016.

Feistritzer, E. (2004). Alternative teacher certification: A state by state analysis 2004. Washington, DC: National Center for Educational Information

G., Goldhaber,Ehrenberg, Ronald, Daniel D., Brewer, Dominic J. 1995. "Do Teachers' Race, Gender, and Ethnicity Matter? Evidence from the National Educational Longitudinal Study of 1988." *Industrial and Labor Relations Review* 48:547-61.

Gislason, N. (2011), *Building Innovation:History, Cases, and Perspectives on School Design*.Backalong Books.

Gonong, G.O. (2017b).*Professional Standards for Teachers/ Developmental NCBTS*. Quezon City

Guskey, T. R. (1981). Measurement of the responsibility teachers assume for academic successes and failures in the classroom. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 32(3), 44-51.

Guskey, T. R. (1987). Context variables that affect measures of teacher efficacy. *Journal of Educational Research*, 81, 41-47.

Guskey, T. R. (2000a). *Evaluating professional development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.

Haggar, H. and McIntyre, D. (2006) *Learning Teaching from Teachers: Realising the Potential of School-based Teacher Education*. Buckingham: Open University Press.

Hargreaves L., Flutter J. (2013) *The Status of Teachers and the Teaching Profession: A desk-study for Education International*. Department of Education, University of Cambridge.

Hatano, G. and Oura, Y. 2003. Commentary: reconceptualising school learning using insight from expertise research. *Educational Researcher*, 32(8), 26-29.

Higgins, S., Hall,E., Wall, K., Woolner, P. and McCaughey,C.(2005) *The Impact of School Environment: A Literature Review*, London: Design Council.

Ingersoll, R. (1999). The problem of underqualified teachers in American secondary schools. *Educational Researcher*, 28, 26–37.

Ingersoll, R. (2000). Turnover among mathematics and science teachers in the U.S. Washington, DC: National Commission on Mathematics and Science Teaching for the 21st Century. (www.ed.gov/americaaccounts/glenn/compapers.html/)

Ingersoll, R. (2001a). *Teacher turnover, teacher shortages and the organization of schools*. Seattle, WA: Center for the Study of Teaching and Policy, University of Washington.

Jalongo, M. R., Rieg, S. A., & Helderbran, V. (2007). *Planning for learning: Collaborative approaches to lesson design and review*. New York: Teachers College Press.

Jurasaitė-Harbiton, Elena & Rex, Lesley. (2010). School cultures as contexts for informal teacher learning. *Teaching and Teacher Education - TEACH TEACH EDUC*. 26. 267-277. 10.1016/j.tate.2009.03.012.

Kahn, W.A. (1989). An exercise of authority. *Organizational Behavior Teaching Review*, 14(2): 28-42

- Kahn, W.A. (1992) To Be Fully There: Psychological Presence at Work. *Human Relations*, 45,321-349. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/001872679204500402>
- Klenowski, V., & Wyatt-Smith, C. (2012). The impact of high stakes testing: the Australian story. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 19 (1), 65-79.
- Klenowski, Val (2012), Sustaining Teacher Professionalism in the Context of Standards Referenced Assessment Reform. In A. Luke, A. Woods & K. Weir (Eds.), *Curriculum, Syllabus Design and Equity: A Primer and Model* (pp. 88- 102). Hoboken: Routledge.
- Kyriacou, C & Kunc, R (2007), 'Beginning teachers' expectations of teaching', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 1246-1257.
- Lee Shulman (1987) *Knowledge and Teaching: Foundations of the New Reform*. *Harvard Educational Review*: April 1987, Vol. 57, No. 1, pp. 1-23.
- Leung, W. (2008). Teacher concerns about curriculum reform: The case of project learning. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher* 17:1, pp. 75-97.
- Macbeath, J. (2012). *Future of Teaching Profession*. Brussels, Belgium: Education International Institute.
- Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates and AERA.
- McDonald, M., & Zeichner, K. (2009). Social justice teacher education. In W. Ayers, T. Quinn, & K. Stovall (Eds.), *Handbook of social justice in education*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Meyer J P, Stanley D J, Herscovitch L and Topolnytsky L (2002), “Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization: A Meta- analysis of Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences”, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 61, pp. 20-52
- Meyer J P, Stanley D J, Herscovitch L and Topolnytsky L (2002), “Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization: A Meta-analysis of Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences”, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 61, pp. 20-5
- Meyer J P, Stanley D J, Herscovitch L and Topolnytsky L (2002), “Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organization: A Meta-analysis of Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences”, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 61, pp. 20-52
- Meyer J, Becker T and Van Dick R (2006), “Social Identities and Commitments at Work: Toward an Integrative Model”, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 27, pp. 665-683.23.
- Meyer J, Becker T and Van Dick R (2006), “Social Identities and Commitments at Work: Toward an Integrative Model”, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 27, pp. 665-683.23.
- Meyer J, Becker T and Van Dick R (2006), “Social Identities and Commitments at Work: Toward an Integrative Model”, *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol.27, pp. 665-683.23.
- Moos, R.H.(1979) *Evaluating Educational Environments*, San Francisco, Washington, London: Jossey Bass.
- National Board for Professional Teaching Standards. (2005). *Studies show strengths of National Board Certified Teachers' assessment and classroom practices*. Arlington, VA: NBPTS. Available at: www.nbpts.org/news/article2.cfm?id=627
- National Competency-Based Teacher Standards– Teachers Strengths and Needs Assessment Toolkit. (2010). Department of Education, National Education Association. (2009). *Teaching outside of your expertise*. Retrieved April 27, 2018 from <https://tinyurl.com/yazfdae3>.
- NEA Foundation. 2005. *Attracting and retaining accomplished teachers in hard-to-staff public schools*. Washington, DC: NEA Foundation for the improvement of Education. Available at: www.neafoundation.org/programs/teacherquality.htm.
- OECD (2002). *Attracting, Developing, and Retaining Effective Teachers*. Paris: OECD Directorate for Education, Employment, Labour, and Social Affairs.
- OECD (2005). *Attracting, Developing ,Retaining Effective Teachers*
- OECD (2008), *OECD Factbook 2008: Economic, Environmental and Social Statistics*, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- OECD (2010). *Innovative Teaching for Effective Learning*, Centre for Educational Research and Innovation. Paris: OECD
- OECD Publishing. Retrieved from http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/pisa2012-results-what-makes-a-school-successful-volume-iv_9789264201156-en
- OECD. (2009). *Creating effective teaching and learning environments: First results from TALIS*. Retrieved April 8, 2018 from <https://tinyurl.com/yb5vjamh>.

- OECD. (2013a). Education at a glance 2013: OECD Indicators. OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/eag-2013-en>
- OECD. (2013b). PISA 2012 results: Excellence through equity (Volume II). OECD Publishing. Retrieved from http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/pisa-2012-results-excellence-through-equity-volume-ii_9789264201132-en
- OECD. (2013c). PISA 2012 results: What makes schools successful (Volume IV).
- OECD. (2013d). Synergies for better learning. OECD Publishing. Retrieved from http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/synergies-for-better-learning-an-international-perspective-on-evaluation-and-assessment_9789264190658-en
- OECD. (2014). TALIS 2013 results: An international perspective on teaching and learning. OECD Publishing. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264196261-en>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (1998). Staying ahead: In-service training and teacher professional development, "What Works in Innovation in Education" series. Paris.
- Popham, W. J. (2004). All about accountability / Why assessment illiteracy is professional suicide. *Educational Leadership*, 62(1), 82-83.
- Republic Act No. 7836. Philippine teachers professionalization act of 1994.
- RIVKIN, S. G., E. A. HANUSHEK, AND J. F. KAIN (2005): "Variable Definitions, Data, and Programs for 'Teachers, Students, and Academic Achievement'," *Econometrica Supplementary Material*, 73, 2, www.econometricsociety.org/ecta/supmat/4139data.pdf
- Ronfeldt, Schwartz, and Jacob (2014), Does Preservice Education Matter? Examining Old Question in New Ways.
- Rothwell, A., Herbert, I. and Rothwell, F. (2007) Self-perceived employability: Construction and initial validation of a scale for university students. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 73, 1-12. doi:10.1016/j.jvb.2007.12.001
- Schultz, P.W. & Zeleny, L.C. (2000). Promoting environmentalism. *The Journal of Social Issues*, 56, 443-457.
- SEAMEO INNOTECH. (2010). Teaching competency standards in Southeast Asian Countries: Eleven country audit. Retrieved March 4, 2017 from <https://tinyurl.com/y7vr3wxf>.
- Shulman, L.S. (1986). Those who understand: Knowledge growth in teaching. *Educational Researcher*, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp 4 – 14.
- Shulman, L.S. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reforms. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1-22.
- Southeast Center for Teaching Quality. (2002). Recruiting teachers for hard-to staff schools: Solutions for the Southeast and the nation. Chapel Hill, NC: SECTQ.
- Stephen Hacket (2001) Educating for Competency and Reflective Practice: fostering a conjoint approach in education and training, *Journal of workplace learning*, vol.13 Issue:3 pp.103-112
- Stiggins, R. J. (2002). Where is our assessment future and how can we get there from here? In R. W. Lissitz & W.D. Schafer (Eds), *Assessment in educational reform: Both means and ends* (pp. 18-48). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Stoeber & Rennert (2008). Perfectionism in school teachers: Relations with stress appraisals, coping styles and burnout.
- Strahan, D. (2003) Promoting a Collaborative Professional Culture in Three Elementary Schools That Have Beaten the Odds. *The Elementary School Journal*, 104, 127-146. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/499746>
- Teacher Leaders Network. (2005). Assuring teaching quality in high poverty, low performing, and hard to staff schools. Chapel Hill, NC: Center for Teaching Quality. Available at: www.teacherleaders.org/Conversations/HTS/HTSintro.html.
- UNESCO (2008). *Overcoming Inequality: Why Governance Matters* EFA Global Monitoring Report 2009, Paris and Oxford: UNESCO and Oxford University Press.
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2006). *Victorian Curriculum and Assessment Authority 2014, F-10 curriculum planning and reporting guidelines*. Melbourne: Victorian Curriculum and Assessment Authority.
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics.van den Berg (2002) 'Teachers' meanings regarding educational practice, *Review of Educational Research*, 72(4): 577-625
- Wan, H., Sulaiman, M., & Omar, A. (2012). Procedural justice in promotion decision of managerial staff in Malaysia. *Asia Pacific Business Review*, 18(1), 99-121. doi:10.1080/13602380903424167
- William, D. February 1997. Evaluation of the Key Stage 3 Diagnostic Software pilot, February, London, , UK: King's College London School of Education. Report prepared for School Curriculum and Assessment Authority
- Williamson McDiarmid, G. and Clevenger-Bright, M. 2008. Rethinking Teacher Capacity. In Cochran-Smith, M., Feiman-Nemser, S.

and Mc Intyre, D. (Eds). Handbook of Research on Teacher Education. Enduring questions in changing contexts. New York/Abingdon: Routledge/Taylor and Francis.

Wolf, Lisa & Ward, Kelly & Kinzie, J. (2009). A Tangled Web of Terms: The Overlap and Unique Contribution of Involvement, Engagement, and Integration to Understanding College Student Success. *Journal of College Student Development*. 50. 407-428.

Wong, P. M. & Wong, C. S. (2010). Promotion Criteria and job Satisfaction of School Teachers in Hong Kong. *Educational Management and Administration Journal* Vol 33 No. 4(423-447)

Yoon, K. S., Duncan, T., Lee, S. W.-Y., Scarloss, B., & Shapley, K.(2007). Reviewing the evidence on how teacher professional development affects student achievement (Issues & Answers Report, REL 2007–No.033). Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences, National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Regional Educational Laboratory Southwest

Zientek (2007) Preparing High Quality Teachers: View from the Classroom. *American Educational Research Journal*, vol.44,4,pp.959-1001.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Dr. Amie P. Matalam

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines